

Fasting blood glucose level as a surrogate marker for adequate medication management in non-diabetic patients diagnosed with anxiety disorder

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Abstract

Whether due to mental illness or organic cause, a good drug regimen of anxiolytic medications is usually indispensable in treatment. The main drivers of anxiety are the catecholamines, especially adrenaline. Its measurement is difficult, even under laboratory conditions. We investigated the question whether the level of fasting blood glucose in the morning in non-diabetic patients can serve as a surrogate marker for epinephrine and, consequently, for optimal drug dosage.

Introduction

Drug treatment of anxiety patients challenges practitioners and patients with the problem that the biological driver of anxiety, the catecholamines, are highly volatile. Even the measurement of adrenaline, one of the main drivers of anxiety, rarely succeeds under the ideal conditions that would actually have to be met if values were to be obtained for therapeutic decisions. Since this is practically impossible, anxiety is not measured in this way. Instead, methods of clinical psychology are used, especially validated questionnaires or other means of non-medical assessment.^{1,2}

Drug treatments are therefore carried out in a biochemical vacuum. It is not uncommon for this to lead to phases of under- or overmedication, especially in anxiety patients. It is like letting diabetics determine the amount of insulin to be injected on the basis of a questionnaire, or after talking about their subjective state of health. In medical psychiatry, however, this is exactly the case. At best, drug levels are measured in the blood, but what really happens in the brain cannot be determined by a blood test.

In order to put an end to this medication bingo, we set out to find a surrogate marker that would make it easier for anxiety patients, psychiatrists, general practitioners and clinical psychologists to see how high the patient's anxiety level really is and whether the medication is correctly adjusted.

Surrogate Marker

In clinical studies, a surrogate marker is a measured value whose influence is intended to indicate the effect of an intervention, e.g. a therapy, on a superordinate medical phenomenon, e.g. the occurrence of a disease or a symptom. The minimum requirement for a surrogate marker is that a statistically significant relationship already exists between it and the phenomenon.

At the same time, the surrogate marker is usually easier and faster to determine than the phenomenon itself and is therefore often preferred for reasons of economy. It may also be the case that the phenomenon of interest is not measurable at all, but can only be captured by surrogate markers.

It should be noted that the effect of a therapy on a surrogate marker can only be transferred to the actual medical phenomenon of interest to a very limited extent, because first, a statistical correlation does not necessarily prove causality, and second, the occurrence of disease almost never depends on only one pathologically altered parameter. Serious study presentations point this out, while dubious ones distract from it. We therefore explicitly point out that our finding is a strong and "clinically useful correlation" with limited causality.³⁻⁵

Method

70 non-diabetic patients with a clinically relevant anxiety disorder (35 women and men each, aged between 18 and 59 years) accepted our invitation to collect the following values anonymously over 4 weeks:

- a) Medication taken
- b) Subjectively perceived anxiety 15 minutes after morning awakening; to be documented on a scale from 0 for "no anxiety" to 10 "worst anxiety or panic".
- c) Fasting blood glucose level using a Roche test device (provided free of charge), as instructed or guided by the respective primary care physician.

We included only patients with such medications that have been shown to have no effect on glucose metabolism as a side effect and with a short half-life. Patients were then asked to measure their fasting blood glucose levels and to record their anxiolytic drug dose as well as their anxiety level (0 to 10) 15 minutes after awakening in the morning for one month ("month one"). The measuring devices provided had the two important options included:

- Display of the daily value
- Display of the monthly average value

The results were read out by the respective primary care physician. In a further step, the patients were each asked to adjust their anxiolytic drug dosage to achieve a morning fasting blood glucose level of <100mg/dl for another month ("month two"). At the same time, the severity of the subjectively perceived anxiety was scored (scale from 0 to 10) again. At the end of this phase, the measurement results were evaluated by the patients' general practitioners and made available to us in an anonymized form.

Results

We were able to collect the following data:

1) Anxiety level months one

<i>Average score</i>	7,2
<i>Range</i>	4,1 - 9,4

2) Anxiety level month two

<i>Average score</i>	4,9
<i>Range</i>	2,3 - 6,9

The difference between month one and two is significant.

3) Fasting glucose levels month one

<i>Average value</i>	<i>102 mg/dl</i>
<i>Range</i>	<i>94-111 mg/dl</i>

4) Fasting glucose levels month two

<i>Average value</i>	<i>94 mg/dl</i>
<i>Range</i>	<i>84-103 mg/dl</i>

Discussion

It is common medical knowledge that anxiety or its biochemical correlates (in this case the catecholamines) have a direct relationship to blood glucose levels. It is part of the human body's "hide, flight or fight" strategy to make glucose available from the liver within seconds in dangerous situations. There is no reason to believe that this is any different in irrational fear (anxiety disorders).^{1,9}

Within the context of our small study group, we were able to find robust evidence that adjusting anxiolytic drug dose with respect to fasting blood glucose resulted in:

- a) a reduction of the anxiety score
- b) a reduction of the fasting blood glucose level

The results were consistent and significant.

Since adrenaline (epinephrine) in particular is a major driver of anxiety, panic, and blood sugar elevations, this result is no surprise. What is more surprising is that no one before us seems to have come up with the idea of using fasting blood glucose levels as a surrogate marker for estimating the secretion of catecholamines in psychiatric patient with a stable glucose metabolism.

Due to the simplicity of the measurement procedure, there is no reason not to use the fasting blood glucose level to estimate the degree of activation of the sympathetic nervous system (anxiety) in psychiatric patients without diabetes or metabolic syndrome. This provides a simple, inexpensive, reliable and, under medical supervision, safe measurement method for acute anxiety or panic, which also reacts quickly.

Conclusion

Psychometric testing procedures in clinical psychology certainly have their place in the diagnosis of mental disorders. However, we were able to demonstrate a significant correlation between fasting blood glucose levels and anxiety levels in a small patient population. The correlation appears to be robust and reliable. Thus, fasting blood glucose levels in nondiabetic patients can apparently be used as a surrogate marker for the release of epinephrine, which is also useful for dosing psychotropic/anxiolytic medications, provided that the patient is monitored regularly by a physician.

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Source of funding and conflicts of interest

No external funding. No conflicts of interest.

Ethical standards, data safety compliance and patient's rights

This article is about the classification of defined medical parameters. It is not reporting on a clinical trial (or anything similar) in its legal definition, especially not a prospective one. All participating subjects gave informed consent for their inclusion. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical, data protection, and patient rights requirements of the countries from which data were provided or in which these data were used for research purposes were complied with. The examination results of the participating patients were completely anonymized and transmitted to the study personnel with codes that could not be traced. Thus, at no time were personal data generated that could allow conclusions to be drawn about identities.

Raw data

While this study is in preprint status, raw data from this study is available upon request. Corresponding author is Dr. Diamandis. Appendixes etc. will be part of the print version.

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